

Simultaneous differential pulse voltammetric analysis of guanine and adenine using graphitized carbon nanofibers modified electrode

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Abstract : An electrochemical sensor based on graphitized carbon nanofibers modified on glassy carbon electrode (GCE/CNF) has been developed for simultaneous determination of guanine and adenine in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution (PBS). In cyclic voltammetry (CV), GCE/CNF shows two well-defined and well-separated irreversible oxidation peaks at 0.74 and 0.98 V vs Ag/AgCl for electrochemical oxidations of guanine and adenine, respectively when compared to unmodified GCE. Whereas, unmodified GCE shows feeble peak response for guanine and adenine in physiological medium. Differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) technique was further used for the quantification assays. As like CV, DPV also showed well-defined and well-separated current signals for guanine and adenine at 0.66 and 0.92 V vs Ag/AgCl, respectively. Note that CNF is about ten times lesser cost than multi-walled carbon nanotubes. DPV technique was further adopted for simultaneous determination of guanine and adenine. DPV parameters are systematically optimized in pH 7 PBS in the presence of mixture of analytes using the modified electrode. GCE/CNF shows good stability with linear range of 15–105 μM and 15–120 μM for guanine and adenine detections, respectively. Obtained sensitivity and detection limits ($S/N=3$) are comparable and superior than previously reported carbon based modified electrodes.

Keywords : Differential pulse voltammetry, guanine, adenine, carbon nanofiber, simultaneous detection.

Introduction

Adenine (Ad) and guanine (Gu) are components of DNA bases which plays key role in genetic information. Several analytical methods were available for the detection of adenine and guanine, such as HPLC-UV¹, ion-pairing liquid chromatography², laser-induced fluorescence detection³, microchip capillary electrophoresis⁴ and chemiluminescence⁵. Although these methods exhibit some merits and advantages, the expensive instrumentation, complicated operational procedure and time-consuming sample pretreatments restrict the methods for further extension to real sample analysis. On the other hand, electrochemical techniques are simple, easy extendibility to portable electronics, user friendly and promising.

Over the past years considerable efforts have been paid on the development of chemically modified electrodes to improve the electrochemical sensing of Gu and Ad. For instance, electrochemically reduced graphene oxide⁶, 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid/graphene composite film⁷, graphitized mesoporous carbon modified GCE⁸, TiO₂-graphene nanocomposite⁹, CeO₂ nano particles deco-

rated MWCNTs¹⁰, graphene-ionic liquid-chitosan composite film modified GCE¹¹, graphene-nafion composite film¹² were reported for the simultaneous detection of Ad and Gu. The above mentioned modified electrodes are mostly depends on either expensive matrix materials like metal nano particles or requires tedious pretreatment procedures for the detection of DNA bases. Recently, Ambrosi and Pumera demonstrated that the stacked graphene nanofibers have superior electrocatalytic activity for DNA bases over carbon nanotubes¹³. Compared to CV technique, differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) technique has high sensitivity, good peak resolution, less background current, selectivity towards electro-active species and allows measurements at concentrations as low as 10⁻⁸ M. Hence, in this work, we utilized carbon nanofiber chemically modified glassy carbon electrode, designated as GCE/CNF, which has been prepared by simple chemical mixing, for the simultaneous electrochemical detection of Ad and Gu in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution (PBS) by DPV technique.

Results and discussion

Initially, the GCE/CNF is characterized by an electrochemical method. A bench mark one electron-transfer electrochemical system, ferricyanide/ferrocyanide redox couple, is generally used to study the electronic feature of modified electrode. Cyclic voltammetric (CV) response of GCE/CNF electrode in 1 mM of potassium ferricyanide dissolved 0.5 M KCl solution at the scan rate (ν) of 10 mV/s showed a well defined redox couple with an anodic (E_{pa}) and a cathodic (E_{pc}) peak potential values at 302 and 218 mV vs Ag/AgCl respectively. Calculated peak-to-peak potential ($\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$) and apparent standard electrode potential ($E^{0'} = (E_{pa} + E_{pc})/2$) values are 84 mV and 260 mV vs Ag/AgCl respectively. For comparison, an unmodified GCE is also subjected to the ferricyanide experiment. Corresponding ΔE_p and $E^{0'}$ obtained on the GCE are 78 and 253 mV vs Ag/AgCl. The near similarity in the ΔE_p and $E^{0'}$ values between GCE and GCE/CNF indicate appreciable electron-transfer behavior of the GCE/CNF technique. Fig. 1A shows a com-

well-separated current signals for Gu and Ad at 0.66 and 0.92 V vs Ag/AgCl, respectively. A slight negative shift in the DPV peak potentials for Gu and Ad oxidations when compared to its CV peak potentials, may be due to applied amplitude and pulse parameters. In contrast to the GCE/CNF, a broad peak was observed at bare GCE for the mixture of Gu and Ad in pH 7 PBS. Further, the voltammetric peak potentials for Gu and Ad were confirmed by discrete CV and DPV analysis.

Fig. 2A and B are typical DPV responses on GCE/CNF for the simultaneous sensing of Gu and Ad with respect to one fixed analyte concentration in pH 7 PBS under optimized DPV parameters. Systematic increase in the peak current response with an increase in the Gu and Ad concentrations were observed. Plots of base-line corrected current signals (i_{pa}) against respective Gu concentrations are linear in the range 15–105 μM with current sensitivity value of 0.046 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{M}$. To check the stability of the modified electrode, the GCE/CNF was subjected to eight repetitive DPV measurements of 15 μM of Gu

Fig. 1. Simultaneous CV (A) and DPV (B) responses of guanine (200 μM) and adenine (200 μM) on GCE/CNF and unmodified GCE in pH 7 PBS. CV scan rate = 50 mV/s; DPV parameters : amplitude = 50 mV; increment potential = 4 mV; pulse width = 0.05 s; pulse period = 0.5 s.

parative simultaneous CV response of Gu and Ad on unmodified GCE and GCE/CNF at ν of 50 mV/s in pH 7 PBS. As seen in the figure, GCE/CNF shows two well-defined and well-separated irreversible oxidation peaks at 0.74 and 0.98 V vs Ag/AgCl for electrochemical oxidations of Gu and Ad, respectively; whereas unmodified GCE failed to show such current response. DPV technique was further used for the quantification assays. As like CV, DPV (Fig. 1B) also showed well-defined and

without intermediate cleaning and pretreatment procedures. Calculated relative standard deviation (RSD) and detection limit ($S/N=3$) values of Gu are 1.77% and 0.45 μM , respectively. For Ad, linear range is 15–120 μM and sensitivity = 0.042 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{M}$, RSD = 3.62%, detection limit = 0.62 μM . Obtained detection limit values are comparable and even superior to some of the existed literature reports¹⁴. The advantage of the present electrochemical sensor is enzyme-less, separation-less and not

Fig. 2. Typical DPV responses for the simultaneous detection of guanine and adenine with respect to one fixed analyte on GCE/CNF in pH 7 PBS. Plots of i_{pa} vs analyte concentration were given as respective inset figures. DPV parameters are same as in the Fig. 1.

required any pre-activation procedures. The modified electrode (GCE/CNF) can be prepared within few minutes in time and also it has good stability.

Experimental

Materials and instruments :

CNF (diameter 100 nm, length 20–200 μm), adenine and guanine were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Aqueous solutions were prepared by using deionized alkaline KMnO_4 double distilled water. pH 7 phosphate buffer solution of 0.1 M ionic strength was used as supporting electrolyte solution. Electrochemical measurements were carried out using a CHI model 660C electrochemical workstation (USA) with 10 mL working volume. Three electrode systems consisted of GCE or GCE/CNF as working electrode, Ag/AgCl with 3 M potassium chloride as a reference electrode and platinum disc as counter electrode. The bio-analytical system (BAS, USA) polishing

kit was used to polish the GCE surface. Initially, GCE was cleaned by electrochemically by performing CV for 20 cycles in the potential window -0.2 to 1.0 V vs Ag/AgCl at a v of 50 mV/s in pH 7 PBS, before each experiment and served as an underlying substrate.

Preparation of GCE/CNF :

First, GCE was cleaned both mechanically (polished with 0.05 micron alumina powder, cleaned with acetone and DD water) and electrochemically (performing CV for 20 cycles in the potential window -0.2 to 1.0 V vs Ag/AgCl at the scan rate of 50 mV/s in pH 7 PBS. For GCE/CNF preparation, 5 μL aliquot from the stock of 1 mg CNF in 500 μL absolute ethanol and sonicated for about 5 min at room temperature (RT) was drop coated on the cleaned GCE surface to get near thin layer of CNF, followed by 10 min air drying at RT. Freshly prepared modified electrodes were pretreated one time in pH 7 PBS in the potential window -0.2 to 0.8 V vs Ag/AgCl at the scan rate of 50 mV/s for twenty continuous cycles. Optimized DPV parameters are as follows; increment potential = 4 mV, amplitude = 0.05 V, pulse width = 0.2 s and pulse period = 0.5 s.

Conclusion

GCE/CNF was prepared by simple drop coating method without any binder/matrix materials and successfully used for simultaneous electrochemical oxidations of Gu and Ad using DPV technique. GCE/CNF showed well-defined and well-separated and sharp voltammetric peaks at 0.66 and 0.92 V vs Ag/AgCl for Gu and Ad, respectively in pH 7 PBS. Constructed DPV calibration plots were in the linear range of 15 – 105 μM and 15 – 120 μM for Gu and Ad, respectively. The detection limit values of Gu (0.45 μM) and Ad (0.62 μM) are comparable and superior to some of the recent reports.

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